

International Seminar
Advances In Food Bio-Preservation
2-4 October 2022

International Seminar

Advances In Food Bio-Preservation, ISAFP, 2022

Tunis Science City, Tunisia, 2nd -4th, October 2022

Pre-Seminar Booklet, version 28/09/2022

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1. PREFACE

ARTISANEFOOD-2019-2023 project is a PRIMA-funded project aiming to develop simple, efficient and /or innovative bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, targeting the reduction and control of food-borne pathogens in artisanal fermented foods with meat or dairy origin.

The International Seminar “Advances in Food Bio-preservation, ISAFBP 2022” is organized in the framework of ArtiSaneFood project. It offers the opportunity for researchers and PhD students to present their research results dealing with the application of natural food preservatives and biocontrol interventions of food (using natural plant extracts and/or lactic acid bacteria, LAB). Multifunctional properties (*in vitro* and *in vivo* assays) of biomolecules recovered from agro-industrial waste and those of LAB were also underlined through a special communication session. Three-minute E-Poster pitches session will be organized for selected posters. ISAFBP 2022 is also an opportunity to attend a fully practical workshop dealing with classic and dynamic modelling in predictive microbiology. The workshop features prominent experts in the field: Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron & Vasco Cadavez, from the Mountain Research Centre, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Braganza, Portugal.

We are grateful to all our colleagues from LR- Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules (ISBST, UMA), LR Livestock and Wildlife IRA Mednine (UG), LR, PATIO (INAT, UCAR), Post-Doc and PhD students for their valuable collaboration. Many thanks to Prof. ElHatmi H, Prof. Hammadi M, Prof. Khorchani, T and Prof. Ben Chaoucha Chekir, R for helping with organization ISAFBP 2022 and making it an interesting event for sharing valuable scientific results between researchers. Many thanks to Dr. Malek BenZid for significant contribution to seminar preparation since June 2022, to Dr. M’hiri Nouha and Prof. Maha Benlarbi for contribution to English reviewing of the booklet.

A special thank to Prof. Fethi Zagrouba (PDG, Tunis Science City, TSC, Tunisia) and all the team of CST for their availability, collaboration and for offering us a guided visits to TSC and to the Planetarium.

The final seminar of ARTISANEFOOD is programmed in May 2023 at The last seminar is to be held in the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança and will be another opportunity to meet in-person with all project partners. You can continue to follow ARTISANEFOOD project via the following links:

<http://ipb.pt/artisanefood/>; <https://facebook.com/artisanefood>.

On behalf of steering and organizing committees, Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua,

Artisanefood Project Lead for Tunisian Team

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2. PROJECT PRESENTATION

ARTISANEFOOD PROJECT: to increase food safety in artisanal fermented milk and dried meat and sausage

Title: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

Acronym: ARTISANEFOOD

Budget: 1.583708 €

Period: 36 months (to be achieved May 2023)

Call: PRIMA-S2-2018-PIC2019

Number: PRIMA/0001/2018

AIMS

The main object of this project is to develop efficient bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, aiming to the reduction and control of food-borne pathogens in 15 artisanal fermented foods of meat or dairy origin produced in Portugal, Spain, Italy, France, Greece, Morocco and Tunisia.

It consists of an integrated risk-based approach sustained by the concepts of:

- (i) extensive tracking surveys in the artisanal food chains, in order to identify origin, routes of contamination, risk factors favouring pathogens' survival, and technological causes for lack of homogeneity in the quality/safety of end-products;
- (ii) biopreservation, whereby functional starter cultures and natural extracts will be assessed as extra hurdles to ensure safety and extend shelf-life;
- (iii) fate studies of pathogens, predictive dynamic modelling,
- (iv) risk process modelling, for the delineation of the most effective biointerventions, optimisation of process variables and norms/standards, and design of quality monitoring tools.

14h30-18h30	Classical versus dynamic modelling in predictive microbiology – Practice using R	Dr. Vasco Cadavez
	4 th October 2022	
8h00-9h30	O2. Omnibus and microbial competition models – Theory (<i>Key-lecture</i>)	Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron
9h30-10h00	Q/R Session Poster Pitches Session 2: E-Poster 14 to E-Poster 29	
10h00-10h30	Coffee Break	
	LACTIC ACID BACTERIA & FOOD BIOPRESERVATION MODERATORS: PROF. HAMMADI, M PROF. KORCHANI T.	
10h30-10h40	O14. Characterization of traditional Tunisian arid zone fermented goat milk, Rayeb, using <i>Enterococcus faecium</i> isolated from dromedary-fermented milk	Khaoula Belguith
10h40-10h50	O15. Photosensitization effect of thyme essential oil for controlling plant pathogen <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> and <i>Alternaria alternata</i> in postharvest tomatoes	Dhekraa Trabelsi
10h50-11h00	O16. Effect of enzymatic hydrolysis on antioxidant activities of milk whey proteins from five different species	Meriem Ben Yagoub
11h10-11h20	O17. Camel milk casein as a potent source of natural antioxidant peptides	Zeineb Jrad
11h20-11h30	O18. Camel skim milk fermented by newly isolated autochthonous probiotic <i>Lactococcus lactis</i> : Quality characteristics and anti-obesity properties	Oufa Oussaief
11h30-11h40	O19. Anti-tumoral activity of <i>Allium roseum</i> compounds on Breast cancer cells MCF7 and MDA-MB231	Yosr Haffani
11h40-11h50	O20. How does dietary pomegranate peels incorporated in concentrate pellets affect lambs' meat quality and shelf life?	Hadhami Hajji
11h50-12h00	O21. Biological control methods against ochratoxin A-producing fungi isolated from grapes	Islem Dammak
12h00-12h15	Q/R Session	
12h15-13h15	Omnibus and microbial competition models – Practice using R	Dr. Vasco Cadavez
13h15-14h00	Lunch	
	SPECIAL SESSION: Multi-functional biomolecules from agro-industrial waste: food bio-preservatives, antioxidants, <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> antidiabetic and anti-tumoral properties	
	MODERATORS: PROF. HANEN NAJAA, PROF. ESSID I, PROF. SIHEM BELLAGHA	
14h05-14h20	O22. Effects of antioxidant biomolecules extracted from agro-industrial byproducts on the prevention of diabetes and diabetic Retinopathy in Tunisian <i>Psammomys obesus</i> model (<i>Key-lecture</i>)	Prof. Rafika Ben Chaouacha-Chekir
14h20-14h30	O23. Anti-diabetic activity of camel milk; findings in pancreatic beta cells	Amel Sboui
14h30-14h40	O24. Effects of olive mill wastewater compound on retinal function and astroglial glutamate metabolic networks in Diabetic	Oumaima Achour

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	Retinopathy <i>Psammomys obesus</i>	
14h40-14h50	O25. Effect of a biomolecule extracted from brown algae on molecular and cellular alterations in diabetic <i>Psammomys obesus</i> at the retinal and systemic level	Oumayma Hammami
14h50-15h00	O26. Evaluation of anti-hyperlipidemic effect and antioxidant activities of carotenoids extracted from halophilic <i>Archaea</i> – Case study of hyperlipidemic mice	Sana Ben Hamad Bouhamed
15h00-15h30	Q/R Session Winner announcement for Poster Pitches Session , Round table discussion & Miscellaneous session	
15h30-17h00	Guided visit to Tunis Science City of and to the Planetarium	Interested participants

4. SCIENTIFIC & STEERING COMMITTEES

Scientific committee

Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Prof. Halima El-Hatmi, ISBAM & IRA, TN
 Dr. Ursula Gonzales-Barron, CIMO-IPB, PT
 Dr. Vasco Cadavez, CIMO-IPB, PT
 Dr. Tenenhaus-Aziza Fanny, CNIEL, FR
 Dr Alessendra De Cesare, Université de Bologne, IT
 Prof. Antonio Valero, Université Cordoba, ES
 Prof. Fouad, Achemchem, UIZ, MA
 Dr. Khaoula Belguith, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Prof. Khorchani Touhami, IRA, TN
 Prof. Mohamed Hammadi, IRA, TN
 Prof. Rafika BenChaoucha Chekir, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Prof. Sihem Bellagha, INAT, UCAR, TN
 Prof. Iness Essid, INAT, UCAR, TN
 Prof. Hanen Najaa, IRA, TN
 Dr. Amel Sboui, IRA, TN
 D.r Yosr Haffani, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Prof. Maha BenLarbi, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Dr. Ridha Ghali, UMA, TN

Steering committee

Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Dr Malek Benzid, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Prof. Mohamed Hammadi, IRA, TN
 Prof. Touhami Khorchani, IRA, TN
 Prof. Halima El-Hatmi, ISBAM & IRA, TN
 Dr. Zeineb Jrad, IRA, TN
 Dr. Olfa Loussaif, IRA, TN
 Dr. Nouha M'hiri, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Dr. Nesrine Rokbeni, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Ms. Wafa Mkadem, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Ms. Ibtissem BenHmidène, ISBST, UMA, TN
 Mr. Mohamed Dbara, IRA, TN
 Dr. Amel Sboui, IRA, TN
 Ms. Afef Mahjoubi, IRA, TN
 Mr. Mabrouk Lanouar, IRA, TN
 Mr. Mourad Smida, IRA, TN
 Mr. Soufiane Errich, IRA, TN
 Mr. Chokri Khorchani, IRA, TN
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Abstract N°: 08 (O8)

Molecular and phenotypic features of lactic acid producing bacteria isolated from Alheira –Portuguese traditional meat product

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Portuguese traditional fermented meat products constitute a valued economic and cultural heritage strongly linked to the identity of the population and to their production areas. The objective of this work was to screen the lactic acid bacteria (LAB) present in alheira - a traditional fermented sausage. Alheiras from different regions of Trás-os-Montes (Bragança, Mirandela, Vimioso, Mogadouro, Vinhais and Valpaços) were isolated and identified by Sanger sequencing of the 16S ribosomal gene region. A total of 17 LAB isolates were characterised in terms of in-vitro antimicrobial capacities against pathogens, acidification potential, production of L-lactic acid and proteolytic activity. Genomic DNA of the samples was extracted, and the primers used for amplification of the 16S rRNA gene were 27f 5'-AGA GTT TGA TCC TGG CTC AG-3' and 1492r 5'-CTA CGG CTA CCT TGT TAC GA-3'. Sequencing reactions used BigDye™ Terminator v3.1 while purification of samples used SAM/BigDyeXTerminator™ bead solution. Capillary electrophoresis was run in SeqStudio Genetic Analyzer. Sequence results were aligned with sequences from the NCBI database, alignments of at least $\leq 85\%$ identity were obtained using the BLAST algorithm. Data was assessed by Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Genetic analysis of samples showed a diverse lactic acid producing microbiome. LABs from the genus *Lactobacillus* and *Leuconostoc* were dominant, found in 64% of samples, while organisms of the genus *Streptococcus* and *Enterococcus* were found in 36% of samples. *Lactobacillus*, *Pediococcus* and *Leuconostoc* presented overall higher inhibition diameters against *Listeria monocytogenes* (PC1=58.2%, PC2=81.6%), *Salmonella typhimurium* (PC1=61.5%, PC2=86%) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (PC1=61%, PC2=85.7%). *Enterococcus* and *Streptococcus* tended to produce higher acidification. L-(+)-lactic acid production was higher in *Lactobacillus*. This work enabled the identification of LAB normally present in a traditional Portuguese product, as well as the desired technological characteristics that they can bestow to the product.

Key words: microbial population diversity, food quality, food biotechnology, microbiome, fermented sausages

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